

EDUCATIONAL ORIENTATION AS A CROSSING

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6972461

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Abstract: This work reverberates felt crossings that were produced in the exercise of educational guidance in a school on the outskirts of the city of Bagé (RS). It seeks to think of educational guidance as a crossing, as a way of forging thought to move critically, from the historical origins, which produced the modern school and the institutional place in a first assistentialist moment of Educational Guidance as devices of government of the conducts of “undisciplined children”, deviant, to other possible arrangements, aimed at the production of other meanings in the art of educating through sensitive listening, dialogue, inventing paths that involve the training of teachers. A journey inspired by Deleuze-Guattarian thoughts,

Foucault and other thinkers of the Philosophy of Difference, who open gaps in this path creating possibilities of a bold philosophical thinking in the experimentation of the care of the self and others in the creation of an ethics and aesthetics of existences . A proposal that challenges Cartesian thinking, proposing new perspectives, new directions for the Educational Guidance Service (S.O.E) exercised in the daily life of schools. In this way, a militant action in the field of Educational Guidance is desired with the affirmation of life and child becomings that transmute in a rhizomatic way, going beyond therapist and assistance practices.

Keywords : Educational guidance; teacher training; disciplinary power; child becomings.

1. THINK ABOUT CROSSINGS

*“My house is not mine, nor is this place mine.
I'm alone and I can't resist, I have a lot to say”
Milton Nascimento*

Crossed by the experiences lived with children and teachers in a school on the outskirts of the city of Bagé (RS), in this theoretical essay, I propose to think of educational guidance as a crossing, a critical displacement, traced from the historical origins, which produced the modern school and the institutional place from guidance as devices to govern the behavior of “undisciplined children”, to other possible arrangements in teacher training.

When thinking about a possible displacement of the institutionalized place by the tradition that delegated the educational orientation, throughout history and pedagogy, at first, an assistentialist place and, soon after, of disciplining bodies that deviate from the normalizing standard, I seek inspiration in the readings that I have been doing Deleuze and Guattari ((2011, 2012).

Readings that potentiate the desire to move thought like a rhizome, a tangle of threads that are created in coexistence like children at school, sometimes connected, sometimes disconnected, and that open up new possibilities to undo what I am expected to do, to undo the that I did until then, that is, to move from the place that I no longer recognize as mine. Invent a non-place in ways of doing everyday school life with children.

As stated by Certeau (2014), everyday practices are expressed in the noise of ways of doing things, in an ethical and political conviction, fueled by aesthetic sensibility. And how can we weave this art? In what war machinery do we *weave* our existences to account for this coextensive, intense and delusional production? It is the composition of intense becomings in which the performative and pragmatic force is effected through the creation of

rhizomatic maps formed by territories, deterritories, strata, assemblages and lines of flight (DELEUZE; GUATTARI, 2011b).

2. OLD GEARS NOISES

It is these lines and forces that move me to propose this writing. With it, I announce the felt estrangement of an institutional place of educational orientation in which I don't see myself, from which I insistently try to escape and invent crossings.

I speak of the place of school education forged by modern thinking that delegates to the school the function of feeding sad forces of disciplinary power, as was said and written by the philosopher Michel Foucault (1984) about disciplinary devices, such as schools, factories and barracks.

For Foucault, modernity constitutes ways of thinking about human subjectivity, it produces certain identities, such as the sick, the insane, the homosexual, and the institutions created to govern such subjects, such as clinics, prisons and schools, which act in the government of human conduct (FOUCAULT, 1979).

The philosopher conceptualizes power as a strategic field of governmentality that involves three dimensions: the set constituted by institutions, procedures, analyzes and reflections, calculations and tactics that allow the exercise of power over populations in a specific and complex way, aiming to create a political economy at the same time. to institute certain apparatuses of knowledge that guarantee balance and internal security. Second, by governmentality the author understands that type of knowledge through which sovereignty and discipline are exercised. And, finally, the result of this process in the state government (FOUCAULT, 2006).

As for the care of the self, Foucault (2010) creates three meanings based on the study of the Philosophy of Classical Antiquity: a certain way of looking at things, of performing actions, of having relationships with oneself, with others and with the world. Which implies, consecutively, a certain way of converting the gaze of the world, of others, to oneself, being attentive to what one thinks, to what goes on in thought. And, finally, the ways in which actions are carried out from one to another; actions by which we assume, modify and transfigure ourselves.

Thus, the care of the self sounds to our ears as an expression of a moral, an ethics and an aesthetic of the subject about himself that, with the Western Christian perspective and modernity, assumes a negative and selfish character, because it is necessary to be mainly concerned with the care of others, of the collectivity, denying oneself as a subject endowed with truth.

Thus, in contemporary times, the movement that is sought is to restore self-care, as: “[...] , a principle of movement, a principle of permanent restlessness in the course of existence” (FOUCAULT, 2010, p. 9).

Portocarrero (2011) also works with the notions of self-government and self-care, indicating that, when Foucault addresses the problem of the subject's relationship with himself, with others and with the truth, he problematizes the subject's self-formation, referring to it. to the question of power as a strategic field of mobile and conflicting relationships. The author states:

The problem is that self-analysis is very difficult. In the first place, because the techniques of the self do not require the same material apparatus as the production of objects, being even techniques on objects that are often invisible. Second, they are often linked to the driving techniques of others. For example, in the case of educational institutions, attention is drawn to the fact that, always, someone is governing others and teaching them to govern themselves. (PORTOCARRERO, 2011 p. 74).

The author uses the concepts of governability and self-care, running through several works by Michel Foucault to base her reflection in a historical way, analyzing situations and institutions and the subject himself, since the 17th century. This philosophical analysis points out some questions about what makes the subject what he is and also about the institutions and the ways in which they act on the government of conduct.

Do schools and prisons have the same configuration? I ask this question based on the speech, in the speech of some children, from my school, when they “cheat” certain rules, when they are called to “confess” or justify inappropriate behavior and at the height of the revolt they say: “This is a prison !”

For order to be maintained, it is necessary to comply with rules, many of them imposed as true, and the subject needs to “fit” in certain standards to be accepted in social life. Whoever is “different” becomes the “deviant” and must be governed, adjusting to the true discourse.

All this reflection leads us to several questions about our actions and the positions we occupy in the daily life in which we are inserted. What leads us to have certain discourses and attitudes? How do we exercise the government of conduct and the care of self and others?

Driving force of the capture machines of the modern state and capitalism. Desiring machines that are coupled to existences, making us an organism within this production: “in its own production, the body suffers for not having any other organization or organization at all” (DELEUZE; GUATTARI, 2011a, p. 20).

According to Barbosa (2014), educational guidance emerged in Brazil in the 1920s, but only on December 21, 1968 it was institutionalized with Law 5,564, which defined the exercise of the profession of educational advisor at the elementary and middle levels of Basic Education. According to the law, the orientation had the character of “assistance to the students” individually or in groups. In those times of military rule, the country was immersed in censorship, surveillance, and violent curtailment of individual and collective freedoms. Disciplinary power acts in governing the conduct of “deviant” subjects, with a view to normalization. Powers that are even more exacerbated when it comes to schools that serve communities considered vulnerable, those that are on the fringes of the system and that are seen as dangerous.

In this way, educational guidance starts to function as a device for governing conduct coupled with the disciplinary school's production machine. Among the technologies for governing the conduct operated by educational guidance, confession practices come into play. All these gears work as devices to govern minds and make bodies docile.

Throughout history, educational guidance has been reconfigured by other movements, assuming other functions, as emphasized by Barbosa (2014, p. 31):

an agent of change, a *therapist* who should *Rogerianly*²⁴ assist problem-students, a *psychologist* who should only work on interpersonal relationships within the school, a *facilitator of learning*, will, little by little, leave these functions/denominations to assume, with more technical competence, its political commitment.

I perceive, daily, noises of these old gears. Developments of the great machine to grind people on the periphery of capitalism: families incarcerated, children removed from family life and sheltered in temporary shelters, because they were identified in a “situation of

²⁴It refers to Carl Rogers, thinker of the movement called Escola Nova, initially unleashed in the United States and that influenced Brazilian thinkers through the perspective he announced of making students the center of interest in teaching.

risk and abandonment". Many of them are illiterate children, but with an incredible ability to read the world and its unjust gears in a country that violently and at the same time masks violence, under a discourse of protecting children's rights.

Historically, the discourses of traditional and critical pedagogies act on the processes of subjectivation and fabrication of teaching as a conductor of the human soul. According to Garcia (2001), this position of critical subject of pedagogies places the teaching subject as an enlightened, sovereign, active, self-reflective, fully developed, emancipated and self-responsible individual, in this sense, fully capable of governing the conduct of students. the students.

With these readings, I came to realize that the actions of children at school point to important clues to think about the relations of power and knowledge produced there. When, for example, children do not go through the school gate, even if it remains open, it is because they govern their conduct, their way of acting through the discourse of what is allowed or not. This is the care for oneself and for others that permeates social relationships and life in institutions such as schools. Our society and school function on the basis of power relations that create certain regimes of truth such as self-discipline.

However, this does not happen without conflicts in everyday school life. Regarding the childhoods of the children I live with at school, I realize that many of them live in a situation of social vulnerability, as described by Frota (2007):

We just have to look around to see boys and girls on the street, begging, prostituting themselves, being exploited at work, with no time to play, suffering all kinds of violence. Is it possible to think that these boys and girls are not children because they do not present all the predicates that are attributed to childhood? (FROTA, 2007, p. 148).

Children live in different circumstances from what we usually understand as childhood. Often, they forge strategies to escape the violence to which they are exposed. They resist the pain and the rules imposed on their bodies and existences. Rules dictated by the standard of normality that disciplinary institutions establish with the aim of making bodies docile. Hence the role to be played by educational guidance in dealing with cases of disobedience that are outside the normality of the school.

I remember Luis. A boy who attended school in 2012, when I arrived at this institution. In a moment of breaking the established rules, I went to talk to him. He was in the courtyard, sitting on a high, chilling wall. I was afraid he would fall down there. I approached slowly and asked him to accompany me. He denied. I tried to convince you in various ways,

without any success. I will never forget that 10-year-old boy, black, from a very poor family, firm in his convictions. My last, threatening argument, believing it would convince him to return to the classroom, was: “If you don't obey the school rules, I'll have to forward your case to the Prosecutor's Office. The judge will want to talk to you.” He looked at me and wiggling his little feet inside his rain boots, he said: “Oh, the judge, let him take it in the ass!”. And I replied: “But he is an authority! How can you say that?! He has power!” And the boy said laughing: “Does he have power? So tell him to pull that tree up.” The tree was immense with deep roots. I was imagining the scene. Indeed he was right: even with all the power Mr. Judge would never pull that tree out of the ground.

These and other occasions, which are not rare, have forced shifts in the way I relate to children. I have tried to do it in another way, listening to them and establishing reciprocal and provisional agreements with them so that they continue in school. I wish to avoid that the punishments applied to them are so severe as to jeopardize their permanence there.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

I feel affected by the things that I experience there with the children and teachers and that are drawing our lives and the school itself, daily. I have tried to fable my political-pedagogical, ethical and aesthetic action, as an educator and educational advisor, trying to escape from majority and minority agencies that appear to be the same at school and on the social plane.

Insurgent bodies invent cuts, interrupt sad flows of the same repetition, forging other, much more vital flows. Children who drag me across, also force me to sabotage the sorrows of being an institutionalized educational counselor.

Occasions are not rare when I feel disconcerted by the unusual responses of children who seem to invent everyday school life, escaping the traps of governing bodies and minds. I realize that, “in the eyes” of many children, school becomes a place where they feel safer, happier, even in the face of the rules and disciplinary actions imposed. Often, they express the desire to be at school, move and move from the shackles, they are open to creating affective bonds among themselves and with the adults who work there.

I believe that the school is still a possibility for them to meet other people who offer them shelter. And it is up to us educators to be open to receiving them, understanding that:

Not all children, however, can live in the country of childhood. There are those who, born and raised in the belts of misery that today surround the big cities, discover very early on that their ground is the hostile asphalt, where they are hunted by cars and where they begin the routine of criminality. For

these children, childhood is a mythical place, which they can only imagine, when they look at toy store windows, when they watch TV or when they watch middle-class kids go by in their parents' cars. When they ask in a pleading tone – do you have a little change there, uncle? – it's not just money they want; it is an opportunity to visit, for a moment, the country they dream of (SCLIAAR, 1995, p. 04).

There are multiple and diverse conditions for the existence of childhoods. Often, the world we live in does not welcome children, does not offer them healthy and dignified living conditions. It is necessary to think about teaching based on the children we deal with at school. Gallo (2003) writes about the figure of the militant teacher who, from his own desert, disobeys the pre-established order.

On the other hand, we can think of the militant teacher. What is the meaning of this militant teacher today, what would he be? I think it would not necessarily be the one who announces the possibility of the new, but the one who seeks to live the situations and within these lived situations to produce the possibility of the new. In this sense, the teacher would be the one who tries to live the misery of the world, and tries to live the misery of his students, whatever misery it may be, because misery is not necessarily just economic misery; we have social misery, we have cultural misery, we have ethical misery, values misery. Even in situations where students are not at all miserable from an economic point of view, they certainly experience a number of other miseries. The militant teacher would be the one who, living with the students the level of misery that these students live, could, from within this level of misery, within these possibilities, seek to build collectively (GALLO, 2003, p. 73).

Militant professors trace existential territories deterritorialized in short-lived passages, but of profound speed and incessant discovery. A cosmos that opens up through looking, feeling, letting oneself be affected and affected without the pretense of exhausting uncertainties, without the pretension of telling the truth, but living the experience and mapping it in a sensitive way.

It is the virtual that is distinguished from the actual, but a virtual that is no longer chaotic, made consistent or real on the plane of immanence that pulls it out of chaos. Real without being actual, ideal without being abstract. We would say that it is transcendent, because it flies over the state of things, but it is pure immanence that gives it the ability to fly over itself, in itself and on the plane (DELEUZE; GUATTARI, 2011b).

Experiencing child becomings (DELEUZE; GUATTARI, 2012). Forces that escape, overflow and flow along the edges, provoke sensations, movements, create other possibilities. For if children want to run, they run, if they want to cry, they cry, if they want to run away, they run. Perhaps, one can measure up to the child. This displacement requires getting rid of an excess of authoritarianism, even being in another position, living “adulthood”.

As Foucault (1999) warns, there is no power without resistance. Subjects can subvert the rules, not recognize the places instituted by the norms that prevent the expansion of powers. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the different movements that take place in the daily life of schools and that show possible resistance strategies. More, suspend judgments and be willing to think differently, and, perhaps, commit to undoing our doings, by making others do things as militant educators who throw themselves in crossings.

Thus, it is no longer possible to reach a whole, a meaning. What is experienced is coextensive, intense and delusional movement. It is opening up to the infinity of sensations. Overflows that move me to invent looks and thoughts beyond what has already been lived. Mapping that has no end, but leaves traces like clues to always start over. Work of art of the existence that is the life to come.

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